

PREVENTION OF DISPERSION ON FLEXURAL STRENGTHS OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTIC APPLYING BY PREPREGSHEETS CONTAINING CNFS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to investigate the variation on flexural strengths of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced plastic fabricated using prepreg sheets containing cellulose nanofibers (CNFs). Two types of CNFs of which the mean fiber lengths of the CNFs were approximately 6 and 22 μm , respectively, while the diameter of those were almost same, were prepared in order to compare the variation on flexural strengths of the specimens of the CFRPs under 3 point bending load. In the experiments, for comparison, specimens fabricated by conventional hand lay-up method were also prepared. The coefficient of variations (C.V.) in flexural strength were evaluated by using universal testing machine. The test result showed that the C.V. were decreased under conditions in which relatively short CNFs contained, while the C.V. were increased under other conditions. The state of dispersion of each CNFs in resin matrix were taken by using confocal microscope. CNFs aggregates were frequently observed when relatively long CNFs were added into resin matrix. These results suggested that the dispersion of CNFs into matrix resin was insufficient when relatively long CNFs were used, resulting in increased variation in the mechanical properties of the composites.

INTRODUCTION

With the rise in environmental consciousness, the demand for lightweight structural materials such as carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) has been increasing significantly⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾. Currently, most structural components made from CFRP are fabricated using unidirectional (UD) prepreg sheets, which are laid up to form the desired shape due to their high productivity and excellent structural integrity. Given that CFRP has a laminated structure with no interlayer reinforcement, preventing inter-laminar defects during fabrication and operation is critical to avoid degradation in mechanical performance. To enhance the interfacial characteristics of CFRP, the authors have previously proposed modifying the matrix resin with cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) and demonstrated its effectiveness using hand lay-up composites⁽³⁾. However, the applicability of CNFs in prepreg lay-up composites remains uncertain due to the difficulty in preparing prepregs with CNF modified matrix resin, as CNFs typically contain around 90% water by weight. . Recently, new types of CNFs that are already dehydrated and have controlled fiber lengths have been developed by Sugino Machine Co., Ltd., making it relatively easy to prepare prepregs with CNF-modified resin. Therefore, the purpose of this study is not only to investigate the mechanical characteristics and internal morphology, but also to evaluate its statistical variability of UD-CFRPs fabricated using both hand lay-up and prepreg lay-up methods, with matrix resins modified by CNFs addition, in order to clarify the applicability of CNFs. The effects of CNF mean fiber length on composites characteristics were also evaluated in terms of bulk density, porosity, and flexural performances.

2. FABRICATIONS AND MATERIALS

2-1. Materials

For hand lay-up composites, thermosetting epoxy resin (JER 828, Mitsubishi Chemical) and unidirectional carbon fiber cloth (UT70-40G, TORAY) were used as matrix and reinforcement material, respectively. For prepreg lay-up composites, unidirectional prepregs were fabricated using the same thermosetting epoxy and unidirectional carbon fiber tow (T700, TORAY). To modify the epoxy matrix, dried CNFs of two distinct lengths (BiNF-i-s Sugino machine) were prepared. The mean fiber lengths of the CNFs were approximately 6 and 22 μm , respectively. Hereinafter, the CNFs are referred to as S-CNF (6 μm fiber length) and L-CNF (22 μm fiber length), respectively.

Fig.1 Example of appearance of CNFs

2-2. Fabrication method for hand layup composite

The fabrication process involved a hand lay-up method using both original and CNF-modified epoxy resins along with six layers of unidirectional carbon cloths. CNFs were added to the epoxy resin at a concentration of 0.5wt% and dispersed via mechanical mixing for 30 min at 10000 rpm. The carbon cloths and epoxy resin were stacked and pressed under a pressure of 0.89 MPa. The stacked assembly was then cured by heating at 80 C for 1 hour, followed by 150 C for 3 hours, resulting in a 2.0 mm thick UD-CFRP laminate. The fiber volume fraction of the hand lay-up CFRP was approximately 60%. The fabricated CFRP laminates were cut parallel to the fiber direction using a diamond cutter to produce coupon-type specimens measuring 100 mm \times 15 mm \times 2 mm. Fig.2(a) shows the example of hand lay-up specimen.

2-3. Fabrication method for prepreg layup composite

The fabrication process involved a prepreg lay-up method using both original and CNF-modified prepreg, along with sixteen layers of unidirectional prepreg sheets. The weight fraction of added CNFs was controlled to match that used in the hand lay-up composites. The prepreg sheets were stacked and pressed under a pressure of 0.89 MPa. The stacked assembly was then cured by heating at 80 °C for 1 hour, followed by 130 °C for 3 hours, resulting in a 2.0 mm thick UD-CFRP laminate. The fiber volume fraction of the prepreg lay-up CFRP was approximately 63%. The fabricated CFRP laminates were cut parallel to the fiber direction to prepare the test specimens, as described in Section 2.2. An example of a prepreg lay-up specimen is also shown in Fig. 2(b).

(a) Hand lay-up specimen

(b) Prepreg lay-up specimen

Fig.2 Appearance of specimens.

2-4. Bulk density and porosity measurement

The bulk densities of the fabricated composites were measured in accordance with JIS Z8807 using distilled water. For each condition, at least 5 specimens were tested. The weight of each specimen was measured in air and in distilled water, and the bulk density was calculated using the following equation:

$$\rho_{sp} = \frac{W_{air}}{(W_{air} - W_{water})} \rho_{water} \quad (1)$$

Where W_{air} and W_{water} are the weight of the specimen measured in air and in distilled water, respectively, and ρ_{water} is the density of distilled water at room temperature. At least 5 specimens were used to calculate the bulk density of the composites.

To investigate the internal pore structure of the specimen, X-ray CT apparatus (1172, Bruker) was used. For each condition, at least 5 cross-sections were analyzed to calculate the areal fraction of internal pores relative to the cross-sectional area, hereinafter referred to as porosity.

2-5. Bending test

The bending strength of the fabricated composites was evaluated in accordance with JIS K7074. For each condition, at least 10 specimens were tested using a three-point bending setup with 80 mm support span. The specimens were loaded until failure, and the flexural strength was calculated using the following equation:

$$\sigma = \frac{3PL}{2bh^2} \quad (2)$$

where P is the maximum load, L is the span length, b is the specimen width, and h is the specimen thickness.

2-6. Short beam test

The apparent inter-laminar shear strength of the fabricated composites was evaluated in accordance with JIS K7057. For each condition, at least 5 specimens were tested using a three-point bending setup with a 10 mm support span. The specimens were loaded until failure, and the apparent inter-laminar shear strength was calculated using the following equation:

$$\tau_{ILSS} = \frac{3P}{4bh} \quad (3)$$

3. .RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3-1. Effect of CNFs length on bulk density, porosity, and dispersion state

Fig.3 shows the bulk density of UD-composites with respect to mean length of added CNFs. The theoretical densities of both composites calculated based on the densities of the constituent materials and their volume fractions are also indicated by solid line. Test results indicate that the bulk density of the prepreg lay-up composites was consistently higher than that of the hand lay-up composites, regardless of the presence or mean length of the added CNFs. By comparing the theoretical and measured bulk densities of both composites, the observed differences mentioned above can not be attributed to variations in the volume fraction of carbon fibers. On the other hand, when focusing on the effect of the differences in mean length of the added CNFs, the use of L-CNFs slightly decreased the bulk density of the composites, regardless of the fabrication process.

Fig. 4 also shows the measured porosity of the UD-composites with respect to mean length of added CNFs. The measured results revealed that the porosity of the composites increased with an increase of the mean length of the added CNFs. In particular, a significant increase in porosity was observed when the hand lay-up process was employed. Previous studies have reported that adding longer fibrous materials to the matrix resin leads to a significant rise in viscosity of resin⁽⁴⁾⁽⁵⁾. In hand lay-up composites using L-CNF modified matrix resin, the formation of internal pores can be attributed to the increased viscosity caused by the addition of longer CNFs.

For detailed investigation, the added CNFs in the modified matrix resin were observed by using a fluorescence microscope and specially dyed CNFs. Fig. 5 shows the dispersion state of S-CNFs and L-CNFs in the modified matrix resin, respectively. When S-CNFs were used, the CNFs were almost uniformly dispersed throughout the matrix by mechanical mixing. In contrast, the use of L-CNFs resulted in the formation of large aggregates within the matrix. These results also suggest that increase viscosity caused by the longer CNFs may have limited the effectiveness of agitation, leading to insufficient dispersion.

Fig.3 Relation between bulk density and mean length of CNFs

Fig.4 Relationship between porosity and length of nanofibers

(a) S-CNFs in matrix

(b) L-CNFs in matrix

Fig.5 Dispersion state of CNFs in matrix resin

3-2. Effect of CNFs length on mechanical characteristics

Fig. 6 shows the mean flexural strength of UD composites as a function of the mean length of added CNFs. The test results indicated that no significant differences due to fabrication process were observed in the original and S-CNFs modified composites. On the other hand, obvious differences in mean flexural strength were observed when L-CNFs were added to the matrix. The mean flexural strength of the prepreg lay-up composites was clearly lower compared to that of the hand lay-up composites. Fig. 7 also shows the coefficient of variation in flexural strength as a function of the mean length of added CNFs. The test results indicated that the coefficient of variation for the hand lay-up composites was consistently higher than that of the prepreg lay-up composites. This can be attributed to the accumulation of errors caused by manual operations, such as fiber waviness due to uneven impregnation, variations in fiber orientation, and other inconsistencies during fabrication. Focusing on the effects of added CNFs, the addition of S-CNFs to the matrix resin reduced the coefficient of variation in the hand lay-up composites and also slightly reduced in the prepreg lay-up composites. When L-CNFs were added to the matrix resin, the coefficient of variation in the hand lay-up composites was still lower than that of the original hand lay-up composites, but slightly higher than that of the S-CNFs modified ones. In contrast, for the prepreg lay-up composites, the coefficient of variation increased obviously compared to that of the original prepreg lay-up composites. These results suggest that using CNFs of an appropriate length is effective in reducing the coefficient of variation in the flexural strength of composites, regardless of the fabrication process employed. On the other hand, it is

suggested that the use of excessively long CNFs not only increases the coefficient of variation in flexural strength but also decreases the mean flexural strength of the composites, regardless of the fabrication process employed.

Fig. 8 also shows the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) with respect to the mean length of the added CNFs. The test results revealed that the ILSS exhibited a trend similar to that observed in the bending test. In particular, when L-CNFs were used in the prepreg composites, the ILSS was significantly degraded compared to that of the other composites. These results suggest that the presence of CNF aggregates and insufficient dispersion may have a more pronounced impact on the mechanical properties of prepreg lay-up composites compared to hand lay-up composites.

Fig.6 Relation between average flexural strength and length of CNFs

Fig.7 Relation between coefficient of variation and length of CNFs

Fig.8 Relation between ILSS and length of CNFs

4.CONCLUSIONS

1. The bulk densities and porosity of the composites were influenced by the mean length of the added CNFs to the matrix resin, due to their effect on the viscosity of the matrix resin, regardless of the fabrication process employed.
2. The mechanical properties of the composites were influenced by the mean length of the added CNFs to the matrix resin, due to their effect on the formation of aggregates. This effect was more pronounced in the prepreg lay-up composites compared to the hand lay-up composites.

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